

Smartomizer – Proactivity and Traceability in Orchard Spray

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INTRODUCTION

Spraying accounts for 30% of costs in specialty crop production and has a direct impact on harvest quality and market selling price. With conventional application equipment, approximately 80% of treatment failure is a consequence of incorrect human use. Errors may entail an excessive release of products that enter the food chain, pollute the environment, or both. Further, it causes dangerous pest resistances, with in many cases over 50% of pesticides not reaching the target organisms but contaminating the environment, with considerable negative effects for biodiversity, bee life, bystanders, and the ecosystem as a whole (Cunha *et al.*, 2012). Thus, H₃O[®], a holistic system of elements as in Fig.1, is presented to combat the application error problem.

Fig. 1. Conceptual H₃O[®] system technology deployment view.

The proactive H₃O[®] system connects physical IoT (*Internet of Things*) devices on the implement side - in this case a *sprayer control system* (SCS) (Fig.1 bottom right) with a control tablet (TAPP) and a *speciality crop gateway* (SCG) in the tractor's cab (Fig.1 bottom left). The SCG contains a global satellite system receiver to guide the operator in real time and to log positioning data during operations for back-office analysis and treatment tractability. Apart, the SCG constitutes a node on the edge network that connects via a cellular link and the Internet to a private Cloud marked *Speciality Crops Platform* (SCP) (Fig.1 top left). This way, farm managers and/or advisors connected to the SCP via web GUI (*graphical user interface*) can perform actions like sending prescriptions and job orders to the tractor operators and machines in the field, as well as

monitoring results and post processing data, for example, to automatically produce the farm book that records all plant protection product treatments. The tractor mounted SCG also enables limited control and traceability of non-data capable sprayers or other implements like simple fertilizer spreader, pre-pruners, disc mowers, *etc.*, which are hooked up to the tractor's *power take off* (PTO). If on the other hand, the implement is a high-end intelligent sprayer, a so called *Smartomizer*, with embedded *sprayer control system* (SCS), the work order contains sprayer configuration data that allows the sprayer's actuators to adjust the sprayer to field and crop dimensions. Moreover, interoperability of the SCP with third parties, *e.g.* with *farm management information systems* (FMIS), is assured through APIs on the basis of REST/JSON (Fig.1 top right).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During spraying application the tablet in the tractor's cab (TAPP) allows real-time job control through both visualization of the application and by receiving warnings in case any critical parameter differs from its expected value (*e.g.* tractor forward speed, *revolutions per minute* (RPM), agitation, pressure). Relaying the machinery and treatment data to the farm management back office allows treatment analysis, while the data is additionally securely stored in SCP database to allow for full treatment traceability. Fig. 2. (b) shows a typical treatment result map as accessible from the back office GUI.

Fig. 2. (a) In cab display with proactive operator guidance system (TAPP). (b) Traceability data of completed treatment in the *Speciality Crops Platform* (SCP).

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